

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN KHMER EPIGRAPHY

INTRODUCTION

A final remark: contrary to the impression Bhattacharya seeks to give, the field of Khmer epigraphy seems to be far from moribund since the 1960s. Other than the works of scholars mentioned in the above pages, Michael Vickery's remarkable study of the Pre-Angkorian corpus is evidence of vigour, as is the recent appearance of two new dictionaries prepared by Philip Jenner, and the corpus of recently discovered inscriptions edited by Vong Sothea; and now, thanks to the impetus of the project led by Gerdi Gerschheimer, the *Corpus des inscriptions khmères*, new studies and previously unpublished inscriptions are beginning to appear in academic journals [Goodall 2011: 60].

The text quoted here is a statement made by Dominic Goodall, one of the leading Khmer epigraphy researchers today, when he reviewed the recent work by Kamaleswar Bhattacharya who has been studying the Sanskrit inscriptions of ancient Cambodia since the 1950s. As Goodall stated, a new era of Khmer epigraphy has begun. Known inscriptions are being re-deciphered with new approaches and incorporated into the

recently discovered inscriptions and archeological accomplishments, and the reexamination of existing theories is underway with more renewed vigor than ever before. In this paper, I introduce some papers published after 2000 and summarize the past and future of Khmer epigraphy.

1. BACKGROUND

What we call “Khmer inscription” for the sake of convenience roughly refers to post-5th century historical texts engraved on materials such as stone and metal ware found in a wide range of mainland Southeast Asia (the area that includes modern-day Cambodia, Vietnam, Thailand, and Laos). Written in letters originating from India, it mainly uses the old Khmer and Sanskrit languages. Although “Khmer inscription” commonly includes the so-called “modern inscription” engraved after the 16th century, I will not cover it in this paper.

To understand the ancient Cambodian regime (generally called “Khmer Empire” or “Angkor Dynasty” or just “Angkor” that constructed the many stone buildings typified by Angkor Wat) and its society, the more than 1,300¹ materials are nearly the only historical and local text materials from that time.

Whether referencing Hendrik Kern’s paper [Kern 1879], which used the ink rubbing of an inscription² and introduced the contents for the first time, or the first full-fledged corpus of inscriptions of Auguste Barth and Abel Bergaigne [Barth 1885; 1893; Bergaigne 1893], there is no doubt that Khmer epigraphy was started by western Europeans during the era of colonialism at the end of the 19th century. Subsequently, École Française d’Extrême-Orient (French School of Asian Studies, hereinafter the EFEO) took the lead in the research. However, I will not get into the details of these initial studies here. The explanations by Claude Jaques and Saveros Pou are useful in understanding basic information on inscriptions and the general sequence of research history [Jacques 2002; Pou 1997].

After Barth and Bergaigne, the research framework was created by Louis Finot, George Cœdès, et al. by mainly using the setting of *Bulletin de l’École Française d’Extrême-Orient* founded in 1901. The 8-volume *Inscriptions du Cambodge* [Cœdès 1937–1966], completed in 1966, is also widely known to those who study pre-modern Southeast Asian history. The inscriptions numbered from inventory numbers K.1 to K.1005 were sorted by Cœdès. The religious history study by Bhattacharya and the works by Sachchidanand Sahai on the administrative mechanism

of Angkor are remarkable achievements built upon these foundations [Bhattacharya 1961; Sahai 1970]. After Cœdès passed away in 1969, epigraphy was continued mainly by Claude Jacques who published a list that went up to K.1050 [Jacques 1971]. However, with Cambodia entering the era of a long civil war during the same period, they had no choice but to suspend or drastically cut the epigraphy work on site. They did continue to study the ink rubbings of inscriptions previously collected by the EFEO, sort and reexamine known historical materials, and conduct linguistic studies. While there were many important studies among them, the research began losing momentum as compared to the times of Cœdès.³ Although the civil war in Cambodia tentatively settled down in 1993, a little more time was needed to stabilize the political situation and much time and labor were required to check and reconstruct the situation of the research environment including the protection and restoration of cultural property. As far as the historical inscriptions are concerned, it is easy to imagine that they had to spend a great deal of time cross-checking against the past data since there were materials that were lost during the civil war, were missing the excavation information even though they were stored in locations such as a conservation office (Fig. 1), and had sustained damage to the engraved surface from inadequate maintenance. The study by Thomas S. Maxwell at the University

Fig. 1

of Bonn [Maxwell 2007d] is one of the efforts to understand the current state of the inscription left intact in the ruins.

2. REBOOT OF KHMER EPIGRAPHY

It was around the end of the 1990s when we began seeing big movements in Khmer epigraphy. What should be noted first is the book *Society, economics, and politics in pre-Angkor Cambodia: The 7th–8th centuries* [Vickery 1998] by Michael Vickery. Having comprehensively reviewed historical inscriptions in the pre-Angkor period (the period before the 9th century when the Kingdom was moved to the Angkor region) and included many new ideas on deciphering inscription, the book can be used as the foundation for research in this field. In particular, his approach to re-deciphering the section written in Sanskrit based on the decipherment of parts written in old Khmer has many points that we should emulate.

The paper published by Jacques in the following year [Jacques 1999b] prompted the resumption after 21 years of the serial publication *Études d'épigraphie cambodgienne*, which he had managed from 1968 to 1978. There, he romanized and provided translator's annotations on ten inscriptions found at Kbal Spean, an archaeological site in Phnom Kulen (Kulen mountain) located in the north of the Siem Reap Province. The existence of these inscriptions was confirmed in a survey in 1968 and, although short by one to seven lines, they allow us to follow the traces of people who performed rituals in the 10th and 11th centuries.

Furthermore, *Nouvelles inscriptions du Cambodge II & III* released in 2001 by Pou is the first collection of translated inscriptions after the civil war [Pou 2001]. Whereas the first volume published in 1989 mainly dealt with modern inscriptions, this book focused on unpublished inscriptions from the pre-Angkor to the Angkor periods and provided French translation and commentary. Although Volume 2 was originally published in 1996, it seemed to have been incomplete because of "financial reasons" and was recompiled in 2001 by combining Volume 2 with Volume 3. As a note, the book is also characterized by the fact that it only translated the old Khmer part without romanizing the Sanskrit part of the inscription.

Under such a trend, it can be said that the working group for Khmer epigraphy called "Atelier de pratiques d'épigraphie khmère," which was held in August 2002 in Siem Reap, was an important milestone for restarting the research. At this conference, in which participants in-

cluded the EFEO, Ministry of Culture and Fine Arts, and the Authority for the Protection and Management of Angkor and the Region of Siem Reap (APSARA) from Cambodia, Silpakorn University from Thailand, and Sophia University from Japan, the list covering from K.1051 to K.1227 was presented by Jacques and information was exchanged on the methods for collecting ink impressions and organizing materials [Gerschheimer 2002].

In 2004, a program called “Corpus des inscriptions khmères” was initiated under the guidance of Gerdi Gerschheimer from the *École Pratique des Hautes Études* (EPHE) and a framework for cooperation was created for researchers from each country to reorganize historical inscriptions and restart Khmer epigraphy. Today, the seeds sown by these activities are bearing great fruits in various forms.

Besides the activities organized mainly through the above-mentioned EFEO, the spread of research in recent years, such as the Greater Angkor Project by the University of Sydney and various results obtained by Cambodian researchers, further makes us anticipate the new golden age of Khmer epigraphy.

In what follows, though there is space constraint, I will introduce some research accomplishments in recent years.

3. RECENT DEVELOPMENTS

3-1. RESEARCH TOOLS

Old Khmer dictionaries include those by Long Seam, Pou, and Jenner [Long 2000; Pou 2004; Jenner 2009a; 2009b]. In particular, Jenner’s dictionary can be regarded as the ultimate version at this point as it considers the works by the former two and includes several examples. As for grammar, in addition to Jenner’s textbook [Jenner & Sidwell 2010], Khin Sok’s handbook is also useful as it lists basic grammar rules [Khin 2007].

In terms of the works concerning Sanskrit, I will not go into common classical Sanskrit, such as Panini’s handbook on Sanskrit, one by one here. That said, as whether the Sanskrit was used in Southeast Asia in the same way as in the Indian world (especially in literature written in Northern India) should be carefully examined, the interpretation of historical materials in India should not be applied indiscriminately to historical materials in Southeast Asia. From that point of view, since the only glossary that compiled examples of Sanskrit in Khmer inscriptions is the one by Bhattacharya [Bhattacharya 1991], one must find the re-

mainder in individual papers.

Elsewhere, new materials, such as the collection of ink rubbings of inscriptions from Angkor Wat [Ang 2013b] and the collection of ink rubbings from Bayon Temple [Somporn & McCarthy 2012], have become available. In addition, there is much to learn from the list of inscription dates compiled by Roger Billard and John C. Eade [Billard & Eade 2006], which attempted to recover the year, month, day, and sometimes even time translated to the western calendar.

Useful websites have also appeared in recent years. The website of the SEALang Project in the United States provides an old Khmer inscription corpus, allowing users to search for examples (<http://sealang.net/classic/khmer/>). Although it appears that all inscriptions are not posted, it is a great reference. In addition, Corpus des inscriptions khmères mentioned above has its own website (<http://cik.efeo.fr/>). Previously, it was a simplified website; however, it was revamped in May 2017. The latest version of the inscription list was posted and, as of April 2017, users can see data, such as the excavation location, the current location, the date it was engraved, and the papers in which it is mentioned, on inscriptions up to K.1360. Considering the large amount of labor that went into creating the list that extends to 111 pages, I feel great respect for publishing of the list. Because the website also provides detailed tables of inscribed characters by vowel, consonant, and numeral, as well as an extensive list of literatures on epigraphy, those who plan to begin studying epigraphy are encouraged to refer to this reference list. Another website of the EFEO, *photothèque de l'EFEO* (<http://collection.efeo.fr/ws/web/app/report/index.html>), provides the old photographic records kept by the EFEO, allowing users to see numerous ink impressions when they search for “estampage,” for example. Furthermore, the archeological sitemap is also sold, if needed, primarily in Cambodia and the distribution map of inscriptions is included in the same series as well.

Finally, the old Khmer inscription textbook by Ang Chouléan [Ang 2013a] is the first authentic textbook written in Khmer, while Sotheara has also conducted epigraphy using Khmer [Vong 2010; 2011]. These studies are expected to be the cornerstones of the epigraphy written in the Cambodian language by Cambodians. I am looking forward to seeing the younger generations of Cambodian researchers who have learned from these outcomes to publish their accomplishments in the future.

3-2. NEW INSCRIPTIONS

In these days, research papers are being released repeatedly regarding

the historical inscriptions that had been known but unpublished, including newly discovered inscriptions from just before the civil war period to recent years. Among them, I will first cover the papers under “Dossier: «Corpus des inscriptions khmères»” published in memorable Volume 100 of the *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* in 2016 (the year of the journal's title is 2014) here. This feature can be considered the current level of attainment of organized epigraphy in Cambodia after the civil war.

The Sanskrit inscription (K.1254), which was discovered in Angkor Borei and is presumed to have been inscribed in the 7th to 8th centuries based on the shape of letters, states that King Jayavarman enshrined the statue of Viṣṇu (Hari). Gerschheimer and Goodall developed an interesting discussion regarding this Jayavarman [Gerschheimer & Goodall 2014]. It has been known from the previous studies on Angkor history that Jayavarman I ruled from 652 to around the end of 7th century and Jayavarman II took the throne in 802; however, the possibility that “Jayavarman I^{bis}” as another Jayavarman in between these two was presented by Cœdès. Although subsequent studies had rejected the possibility, it gained attention again after the name “Jayavarman” was found in the inscription (K.1236) from the year 763 discovered at Prasat Kampoul Ta Non Temple in Phnom Bayang in Southern Cambodia [Goodall 2012: 353–354]. It is said that this Jayavarman I^{bis} might have been the one to enshrine the statue of Viṣṇu referenced in K.1254. While the most commonly accepted theory based on the past studies is that the mark of Jayavarman II can be traced up to around the year 770, there may be a major change to the descriptions of the period around this time. Since they are specialists of classical Indian literature and Tantra study, these two authors also introduced similar examples found in Indian literatures that are useful for deciphering the inscriptions.

Next, Christophe Pottier and Dominique Soutif's article examined in detail vocabulary usage of the inscription (K.1278) discovered in the small building attached to Bakong, the central temple in Roluos Area located in southeast of the Angkor region, which is written in old Khmer and lists individuals and items that might have been dedicated to the temple. Since there has been a discussion of the history of the Bakong Temple's formation from the standpoint of architecture and archeology as this inscription was reused as a building material, it is also interesting in terms of the interdisciplinary interpretation of inscription [Pottier & Soutif 2014].

As I will discuss the re-decipherment of K.237 inscription by Julia Estève in next section, then I will take up Jean-Baptiste Chevance's work

which deciphered a short inscription discovered in Phnom Kulen [Chevance 2014]. He considers the aforementioned paper by Jacques [Jacques 1999b] and shows that various people have performed religious ceremonies at this Phnom Kulen and Kbal Spean from ancient to modern times. In addition, two other studies of modern inscriptions are included in “Dossier: «Corpus des inscriptions khmères»” [Antelme 2014; Weber 2014].

As described, the *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* is expected to continue playing an important role as the forefront of Khmer epigraphy. The journal contains many other papers to be read. For example, Estève and Soutif considered the latest inscriptions and reexamined the buildings (āsrama) that King Yaśovarman I had constructed throughout the country at the end of the 9th century [Estève & Soutif 2010–2011]. Arlo Griffiths, who extensively studies not only Khmer inscriptions but also inscriptions from Java, Champā, and Burma, worked with Soutif and examined a privately-owned inscription (K.1238), which was discovered in Bangkok, although the original location is unknown [Griffiths & Soutif 2008–2009]. It is presumed to have been originally located in the northwestern part of current Cambodia based on the examples of place names and individuals mentioned in the inscription. Dated to 1036, this inscription claims the legitimacy of the rights of the individual named Loñ Śriviṣṇu and his family under the rule of King Sūryavarman I in the first half of the 11th century. Like this one, inscriptions on which dignitaries claim the legitimacy of their family lines are found often from around the 11th century. It is probably a reflection of a major social change at this time, and K.1238 will be one of the important clues used to examine this issue.

Griffiths and Soutif had put together a special feature called “Dossier: Mobilier de culte inscrit de l'Asie du Sud-Est ancienne,” which includes four papers on inscriptions from Khmer, Champā, and Indonesia, in Volume 69 of *Arts Asiatiques* published in 2014. In the paper on Khmer inscriptions, Estève and Soutif examined inscriptions on liṅgakośa (metallic cover to decorate liṅga) in detail by researching examples extensively [Estève & Soutif 2014]. Griffiths and Vincent also looked at a vase with a Khmer inscription discovered in central Vietnam and provided a detailed description on new findings related to the Mahīdharapura, blood relatives of King Jayavarman V at the end of the 11th century, and Buddhism at this time by using relevant inscriptions [Griffiths & Vincent 2014].

Arts Asiatiques also had a special feature on Khmer inscriptions in Volume 65 published in 2010. It contained three papers, including an

examination on the inscription on a bronze dagger housed at the Museum of Fine Arts of Boston [Gerschheimer & Vincent 2010], a paper on a silver pendant with an inscription that includes a date of 1218 to 1219, which is at the end of the King Jayavarman VII era [Soutif 2010], and a paper that explained the trace of Tantrism in Cambodia, such as vajrasattva, based on inscriptions seen in Buddhist end-pieces [Estève & Vincent 2010]. The inscriptions listed here, like the ones seen on utensils, connect studies of historical text and material culture; the method of multifaceted examination can clarify how people lived at the time more than the content described in the inscription itself suggests. Furthermore, Jacques' examination of the inscription on silverware also presents a previously unknown aspect of the social and political situation during the Jayavarman VII era [Jacques 2003].

In addition to these, Goodall has translated an inscription (K.1049) from the mid-10th century discovered at Phnom Thom in Battambang Province [Goodall 2016]. Although the inscription is short with 10 lines, it is interesting to know the religious practice at the time since the content suggests that the occurrence of Śaiva religious professionals who lived in caves. Furthermore, the onomastic analysis is also conducted in detail, demonstrating that the practice of appending the word “śiva” at the end of a person's name was popular in the 10th century, for example. The note that emphasizes the association with Mantramārga, or Tantric Śaivism, demonstrates the capability of an author who has studied continually initial Tantric literatures, such as *Niśvāsātattvasaṃhitā*. As a note, users can register and download the paper in PDF from the UDAYA: Journal of Khmer Studies website (<http://yosothor.org/udaya/index.php/ujks/issue/archive>). One should also reference this journal when exploring the latest Khmer inscriptions.

The discussion by Maxwell, also published in UDAYA [Maxwell 2009], examined the inscription found at Banteay Chmar, an important archaeological site in the northwestern part of Cambodia.

Elsewhere, Pou, mentioned above, also continued activities and published the fourth volume of *Nouvelles inscriptions du Cambodge* in 2011, translating and annotating 19 Khmer inscriptions from the 8th century to the early modern times [Pou 2011]. As far as modern inscriptions are concerned, Olivier de Bernon also translated in his several papers the inscriptions which had been newly discovered or whereabouts of which had been confirmed anew [Bernon 2001; 2002; 2005].

There are many studies that cannot be mentioned here due to space limitations. At the same time, it seems that there are many studies that have only been presented in the form of handouts distributed

at oral presentations at the workshop and that have not been published yet. Thanks to the decipherments of these new inscriptions, the re-decipherment of known inscriptions is also progressing and a new horizon is appearing through examinations from the perspective of multiple disciplines at the same time. As we further revise the existing historical viewpoints, more probable descriptions will become available.

3-3. NEW APPROACHES, NEW DECIPHERMENTS

It is also necessary to re-decipher known, published inscriptions based on newly-discovered historical materials and the development of relevant sciences such as archeology and art history. At the same time, new approaches based on the use of digital databases are emerging. In addition to the aforementioned SEAlang, the EFEO and the University of Sydney are also undertaking digital archiving of the inscription data and exchanging opinions to advance this area [Estève 2010–2011].

Manuel d'épigraphie du Cambodge by Ishizawa Yoshiaki, Jacques, Khin, et al. has translations and commentaries on nine inscriptions, which includes new ones [Jacques & Khin 2007]. The collection of English translations of Sanskrit inscriptions by Bhattacharya mentioned at the beginning of this paper [Bhattacharya 2009] has retranslated known inscriptions found at five archaeological sites that are primarily from the pre-Angkor period. As Goodall stated, caution is required when using the translation since Bhattacharya introduced new inscription decipherments without a footnote [Goodall 2011: 49]; however, given that the translation of inscriptions is often done in French, it would attract a wider range of readers in that sense. Likewise, while Ta Prohm Inscription, an important inscription of the Jayavarman VII era, has been translated and published in English [Kapur & Sahai 2007], verification by readers is required as there is no footnote.

In addition, the English translation of Sdok Kak Thom Inscription [Sak-Humphry 2005] has a distinguishing quality particularly in the commentary on the grammar of the Khmer part. Reexamination of Preah Khan Inscription by Maxwell has advanced the research on this inscription thanks to its extensive footnotes [Maxwell 2007a]. His summary of short inscriptions left at the temples from the Jayavarman VII era is also useful [Maxwell 2007c].

Reexamination of inscribed historical materials based on specific viewpoints and interests is also underway. Alexis Sanderson compared Khmer inscriptions to manuscripts from India and Nepal to discuss extensively about Śaivism, which was the dominant religion at the time,

making it fundamental literature for the religious history of the Angkor period [Sanderson 2003].

The re-deciphering of the K.237 inscription (Prasat Preah Khsaet, Siem Reap Province) by Estève [Estève 2014] accompanies discussion about religious mixing, which is the author's area of specialty. Dated to 1066, the inscription shows an interesting case about the relationship between Hinduism and Buddhism at the time. According to the inscription, the statues of Śiva (liṅga), Viṣṇu, Brahmā, and Buddha were enshrined and this has been interpreted as a practice for worshiping religiously the combined four deities *caturmūrti*. Meanwhile, Estève elaborates upon the distinction and non-discrimination as well as the mixture and coexistence of each religion by taking into consideration the discussions of *Kaṃraten Jagat*, which is believed to be a deity that reflects the indigenous faith of Cambodia.

Eade, who specializes in Indian and Southeast Asian calendrical systems, described in detail the astronomical interpretation over the age of K.121 discovered in Preah Theat Khvan Pir in Kratie Province [Eade 2005]. Chhom Kunthea is reexamining the famous Vat Luong Kau inscription found near the Wat Phu ruins located in current Laos. While the inscription is about the king named Devānīka (Mahārājādhirāja) enshrining “tīrtha” called Kurukṣetra, this paper reexamines the meaning of “tīrtha” by referring to Indian literature and Khmer inscriptions [Chhom 2005]. She also comprehensively re-deciphers the inscribed historical materials left at the Koh Ker ruins, which was built as an imperial capital during the 8th century [Chhom 2011]. Several “noname” inscriptions not included in the past inventories are noted in the book; however, it seems that these are the ones included in K.1300 to K.1312 in the latest inventory mentioned above. In terms of the Koh Ker ruins, a panel report has been presented by Jacques and others at the 15th International Conference of the European Association of Southeast Asian Archaeologists held in Paris in June 2015 suggesting that new results may be published soon. Ian Lowman re-deciphered the Benteay Chmar inscription (K.227) and presented the possibility that part of the temple's bas-relief was a sacred biography of Jayavarman VII [Lowman 2012]. Michel Ferlus used an old Khmer inscription from a linguistics perspective and published an article on communication in ancient times as seen from names of old places and the exchanges of words [Ferlus 2012a; 2012b]. Amandine Lepoutre, an expert on Champā inscriptions, conducted a comparative investigation of Champā and Khmer historical materials and discussed the relationship between these two countries during the Jayavarman VII era [Lepoutre 2013].

Using the Greater Angkor Project promoted by the University of Sydney as a starting point, Eileen Lustig is developing a quantitative analysis that uses the databases of inscribed historical materials. Analysis of aspects such as the distribution trend of inscriptions related to land transactions done by mapping the number of vocabularies used and their distributions by era [Lustig et al. 2007] is an area these research approaches are good at. While there are many difficulties that need to be overcome, such as the small sample size, the handling of inscriptions with unknown origin, and the measurement of the results of qualitative studies, it is desirable to have more materials that can contribute to examination. As for the quantitative analysis on the so-called “slaves” listed in inscriptions (group of individual names listed on the list of offerings to the temple), it is very interesting since it suggests social changes such as shifts in gender roles from the Jayavarman IV era in the early 10th century [Lustig & Lustig 2013].

As a note, there are some doctoral theses by the researchers mentioned in this article [Estève 2009; Lustig 2009; Soutif 2009a; Vong 2017] that I did not cover although they are included in the Select Bibliography. These studies are the pursuit of each researcher’s main interests and concerns and are themes likely to be addressed in the future. They may be largely revised and further expanded upon as the current research evolves. I will look forward to the day when those results are published as books.

Let me end this section with a brief review of the study of Khmer epigraphy in Japan. The first in-earnest study in the field was done in 1965 by Kanayama Yoshio in his analysis of occurrences in the literature of the term “*pura*” (city) used as a regional territorial unit during the Angkor Period, in order to shed light on one aspect of social structure at the time [Kanayama 1965]. After Kanayama’s untimely death, it was Ishizawa Yoshiaki who took the lead in the study of Cambodian ancient history, also contributing greatly to the preservation of cultural properties and the training of the next generation of scholars, including myself [Matsuura 2014], to expand the field into new areas. In the field of epigraphy, Ishizawa is best known for his study of Angkor social institutions through an investigation of the usage of “title nouns” in the sources [Ishizawa 2013]. My own work has included not only textual analysis of the inscriptions, but also a technological study into the possibilities of making digital rubbings using a three-dimensional scanner (see Fig. 2). To be perfectly honest, however, the present situation of the study of Khmer epigraphy in Japan still remains in the developing stages, including the aspect of information exchange with our American and European colleagues.

Fig. 2

4. FINAL REMARK

Due to space constraints, I was only able to cover some of the discussions of inscription decipherments in this paper. Studies from various fields such as archeology, architecture, and art history are undoubtedly expanding considerably by referring to these inscription decipherments.

Now that it has almost been 140 years since Khmer epigraphy was started, the foundation built by the previous generation of researchers are being comprehensively reviewed, and the history of ancient Cambodia and various aspects of exchanges over South and Southeast Asia derived from inscription decipherments are being reconstructed. However, it only means that we are at the starting line; there are many challenges to be overcome. Although the results of Barth and Bergaigne at the end of the 19th century are a pioneering and monumental achievement, these need to be reviewed from a contemporary perspective including transliteration. Deciphering inscriptions requires much time and labor. At the same time, there are ambiguities in the content and a range of interpretations where the intended meaning cannot be confirmed. In that respect, the fact that many researchers in recent years are carefully supplementing the basis of decipherment by using footnotes and other

means should be highly praised. In addition, the results of these inscription studies further increase its value when used by researchers in other fields. In that sense, various gimmicks are required concerning how the outcome should be presented to those who do not specialize in epigraphy. Many of the accomplishments introduced in this paper are co-authored with researchers such as archaeologists. If this trend continues, a new horizon will open for Khmer epigraphy.

Finally, as is well known, inscriptions are biased historical materials incidentally left by the elite who performed religious acts. The content is full of ambiguity and hints, making examinations from various angles essential. Above all, calm debates are crucial in deciphering inscriptions. I hope open discussions will continue in the future while maintaining an appropriate distance from political situations and nationalism of the modern society as well as academic authoritarianism.

*—Originally written in Japanese
Translated by the Toyo Bunko*

NOTES

- 1 Khmer inscriptions are currently organized by the inventory number starting with “K” and, as described later, up to K.1360 of them have been verified as of April 2017. Since there are cases in which multiple texts are grouped together under one K number, “more than 1,300” is a tentative figure.
- 2 Han Chey inscription (K.81) in Kompong Cham province, Cambodia.
- 3 Then again, according to Bhattacharya, the scholars of the times of Cœdès were too impatient. “The older scholars were in a hurry to make the document available, and they did that with an extraordinary rapidity as we have seen. They, therefore, had no time to acquire that knowledge of the Sanskrit language and culture it was necessary to acquire to understand fully and correctly the texts they were deciphering and translating” [Bhattacharya 2004: 215].

SELECT BIBLIOGRAPHY

Ang Chouléan អាំង ជួលាន. 2013a. *មូលដ្ឋានអ្នករៀនខ្មែរបុរាណ* (Basics on old Khmer epigraphy). Phnom Penh: Yosothor. 282p.

- . 2013b. *Inscriptions of Angkor Wat: Ancient, middle and modern periods*. Phnom Penh; Siem Reap: APSARA Authority; Center for Khmer Studies. 193p.
- Antelme, Michel. 2010. Quelques nouvelles pistes de recherche sur l'étymologie du nom Tchen-la. *Péninsule* 61:11–43.
- . 2011. Quelques considérations sur deux mesures de capacité en vieux khmer et leurs possibles équivalents en khmer moderne: les cas de tloñ, thloñ, thlvañ ou tanloññ (etc.) et dnal. *Journal Asiatique* 299-1:319–367.
- . 2012. Des Varṇaśrama Angkoriens aux peuples péariques du Cambodge post-Angkorien: Une possible trace d'une institution angkoriennne dans le lexique moderne et contemporain. *Péninsule* 65:101–144.
- . 2014 (actually published in 2016). Les estampeurs khmers d'Aymonier et leur production épigraphique connue (K.1089.1, K.1089.2, K.1134, K.1135, K.1136, et K.1137). *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 100:231–252.
- Barth, Auguste. 1885. Inscriptions sanscrites du Cambodge. *Notices et Extraits des Manuscrits de la Bibliothèque Nationale et Autres Bibliothèques* 27-1, fasc. 1:1–80.
- . 1893. Note additionnelle au sujet des dates contenus dans les inscriptions du Cambodge du 1^{er} fascicule et dans les inscriptions de Campā. *Notices et Extraits des Manuscrits de la Bibliothèque Nationale et Autres Bibliothèques* 27-1, fasc. 2:589–604.
- Bergaigne, Abel. 1893. Inscription sanscrites du Cambodge. *Notices et Extraits des Manuscrits de la Bibliothèque Nationale et Autres Bibliothèques* 27-1, fasc. 2:293–588.
- Bernon, Olivier de. 2001. Le plus ancien édifice subsistant de Phnom Penh: Une tour angkoriennne sise dans l'enceinte du Vatt Uṇṇalom. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 88:249–260.
- . 2002. L'inscription K.1212 du Vatt Samrong Ek dans la province de Tra Vinh au Viêt-nam. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 9:35–46.
- . 2005. Note sur l'inscription du vatt Brai Buoij K.481. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 92:525–544.
- Bhattacharya, Kamaleswar. 1961. *Les religions brahmaniques de l'ancien Cambodge d'après l'épigraphie et l'iconographie*. Paris: École Française d'Extrême-Orient. 200p.
- . 1991. *Recherches sur le vocabulaire des inscriptions sanscrites du Cambodge*. Paris: École Française d'Extrême-Orient. 89p.
- . 2004. The present state of work on the Sanskrit epigraphy of Cambodia. *Udaya: Journal of Khmer Studies* 5:213–217.
- Bhattacharya, Kamaleswar and Karl-Heinz Golzio. 2009. *A selection of Sanskrit inscriptions from Cambodia*. Siem Reap: Center for Khmer Studies. 187p.
- Billard, Roger, and John C. Eade. 2006. Dates des inscriptions du pays

- khmer. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 93:395–428.
- Bourdonneau, Éric. 2012. L'histoire du Cambodge ancien existe-t-elle?: Monuments et documents de «dix siècles inconnus». *Péninsule* 65:217–244.
- Chakravarti, Adir. 1980. *The Sdok Kak Thom Inscription*. 2 vols. Calcutta: Sanskrit College.
- Chevance, Jean-Baptiste. 2014 (actually published in 2016). Inscriptions du Phnom Kulen: Corpus existant et inscriptions inédites, une mise en contexte. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 100:201–230.
- Chhom Kunthea. 2005. The inscription of Vāt Luang Kāu viewed from Kurukṣetra, India. *Sikṣācakr: Journal of the Center for Khmer Studies* 7:46–52.
- . 2011. *Inscriptions of Koh Ker I*. Budapest: Hungarian Southeast Asian Reserch Institute. 334p.
- Cœdès, George. 1937–1966. *Inscriptions du cambodge*. 8 vols. Hanoi-Paris: École Française d'Extrême-Orient.
- Corpus des Inscriptions Khmères. 2008–2009a (actually published in 2012). «Les Śivapāda du Cambodge», un atelier présenté à la 12^e conférence internationale de la European Association of Southeast Asian Archaeologists (EurASEAA) à Leyde (Pays-Bas), le 4 septembre 2008. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 95–96:425–429.
- . 2008–2009b (actually published in 2012). Une exposition d'inscriptions préangkorienues au musée national du Cambodge de Phnom Penh. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 95–96:431–433.
- Eade, John C. 2005. The astronomy of K.121. *Sikṣācakr: Journal of the Center for Khmer Studies* 7:40–45.
- Estève, Julia. 2009. Étude critique des phénomènes de syncrétisme religieux dans le Cambodge angkorien. PhD diss., École Pratique des Hautes Études.
- . 2010–2011 (actually published in 2013). “New approaches to old texts: Cambodian inscriptions in the digital age,” une conférence internationale organisée par le *Corpus des inscriptions khmères*, l'APSARA et l'Université de Sydney. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 97–98:403–405.
- . 2014 (actually published in 2016). L'inscription K.237 de Prāsāt Preaḥ Khsaet: Une *caturmūrti* insolite? *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 100:167–200.
- Estève, Julia, and Brice Vincent. 2010. L'about inscrit du musée national du Cambodge (K.943): Nouveaux éléments sur le bouddhisme tantrique à l'époque angkorienne. *Arts Asiatiques* 65:133–158.
- Estève, Julia, and Dominique Soutif. 2010–2011 (actually published in 2013). Les Yaśodharāśrama, marqueurs d'empire et bornes sacrées: Conformité et spécificité des stèles digraphiques khmères de la région de Vat Phu. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 97–98:331–355.

- . 2014. Un lîngakośa inscrit au Musée national du Cambodge (K.1286). *Arts Asiatiques* 69: 97–106.
- Ferlus, Michel. 2012a. Origine des anciens noms du Cambodge: Fou-nan et Tchen-la: L'interprétation des transcriptions chinoises. *Péninsule* 65:47–64.
- . 2012b. Linguistic evidence of the trans-peninsular trade route from North Vietnam to the Gulf of Thailand (3rd–8th centuries). *Mon-Khmer Studies* 41:10–19.
- Filliozat, Vasundhara. 2002. Indian epigraphy and its influence on Cambodia. *Sikśācākṛ: Newsletter of the Center for Khmer Studies* 5:12–15.
- Gerschheimer, Gerdi. 2002. Atelier de pratiques d'épigraphie khmère (Siem Reap, 26–29 août 2002). *Bulletin de l'École française d'Extrême-Orient* 89:361–363.
- . 2003. Les Corpus des inscriptions khmères. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 90–91:478–482.
- . 2006. L'inscription de Dharmasena à Mueang Toei (K.1082): 2. Épigraphie. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 18:93–106.
- Gerschheimer, Gerdi and Brice Vincent. 2010. L'épée inscrite de Boston (K. 1048, 1040–41 de notre ère). *Arts Asiatiques* 65:109–120.
- Gerschheimer, Gerdi, and Dominic Goodall. 2014 (actually published in 2016). «Que cette demeure de Śrīpati dure sur terre...»: L'inscription préangkorienne K.1254 du musée d'Angkor Borei. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 100:113–146.
- Golzio, Karl-Heinz. 2009. Was the inscription K.49 from Vāt Prei Vāl really Buddhist? *Sikśācākṛ: Journal of Cambodia Research* 11:9–11.
- Goodall, Dominic. 2011. Book review: Bhattacharya, Kamaleswar (ed.), in collaboration with Karl-Heinz Golzio, *A selection of Sanskrit inscriptions from Cambodia* (Siem Reap: Center for Khmer Studies, 2009). *Indo-Iranian Journal* 54:49–60.
- . 2013. Les influences littéraires indiennes dans les inscriptions du Cambodge: l'exemple d'un chef-d'œuvre inédit du VIII^e siècle (K.1236). *Comptes Rendus des Séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres* 2012, no. 1 (janvier–mars):345–357.
- . 2016. On K.1049, a tenth-century cave-inscription from Battambang, and on the sectarian obedience of the Śaiva ascetics of non-royal cave-inscriptions in Cambodia. *Udaya, Journal of Khmer Studies* 13:3–34.
- Griffiths, Arlo, John C. Eade, and Gerdi Gerschheimer. 2005. La stèle d'installation de Śrī Tribhuvaneśvara: Une nouvelle inscription préangkorienne du Musée de Phnom Penh (K.1214). *Journal Asiatique* 293-1:11–43.
- . 2009. Sūrya's Nāgas, Candra's square seat and the mounted bull with two guardians: Iconographical notes on two Khmer illustrated stela inscriptions. In *Prajñādhara: Essays on Asian art, history, epigraphy and culture in honour of Gouriswar Bhattacharya*, ed. Gerd J. R. Mevis-

- sen and Arundhati Banerji, 466–478. New Delhi: Kaveri Books.
- Griffiths, Arlo, and Brice Vincent. 2014. Un vase khmer inscrit de la fin du XI^e siècle (K.1296). *Arts Asiatiques* 69:115–128.
- Griffiths, Arlo, and Dominique Soutif. 2008–2009 (actually published in 2012). Autour des terres du Loñ Śrīviṣṇu et de sa famille: Un document administrative du Cambodge angkorien, l’inscription K.1238. *Bulletin de l’École Française d’Extrême-Orient* 95–96:29–72.
- Groslier, Bernard Philippe. 1973. *Inscriptions du Bayon*. Paris: École Française d’Extrême Orient.
- Haendel, Alexandra. 2005. The divine in the human world: Sculpture at two tenth-century temples at Angkor. *Artibus Asiae* 65-2:213–252.
- Hawixbrock, Christine. 2012. La stèle inscrite K.1320: Note sur une nouvelle découverte archéologique à Vat Phu. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 30:103–119.
- Ishizawa Yoshiaki 石澤良昭. 1979. Hikoku shiryō to rekishi kōsatsu: Kanbojia hibun, Chanpā hibun no jirei kara 碑刻史料と歴史考察:カンボジア碑文・チャンパー碑文の事例から (Réflexion sur les structures de l’ancien Cambodge et l’ancien Champa à partir des sources épigraphiques). *Nampō Bunka* 『南方文化』 (Tenri Bulletin of South Asian Studies) 6:49–87.
- . 2003. Kanbojia-shi no kōchiku ni mirareru hikokubun shiryō: Yureugoku Kenkyū seika wo saikakunin カンボジア史の構築に見られる碑刻文史料:揺れ動く研究成果を再確認 (Inscription in the construction of Cambodian history: Reconsideration of ever-changing research results). In *Rekishika no kōbō* 『歴史家の工房』 (A historian’s atelier: Approaching the past through historical evidence), ed. Ōsawa Masaaki 大澤正昭, 145–167. Tokyo: Jōchi Daigaku Shuppan 上智大学出版.
- . 2013. *Shin kodai Kanbojia-shi kenkyū* 『〈新〉古代カンボジア史研究』 (New research on history of ancient Cambodia). Tokyo: Fūkyōsha 風響社.
- Ishizawa Yoshiaki, Claude Jacques, and Khin Sok. 2007. *Manuel d’épigraphie du Cambodge (avec la collaboration de Uraisi Varasarin, Michael Vickery, Tatsuro Yamamoto)*. Paris: École Française d’Extrême-Orient; UNESCO. 215p.
- Iwamoto Yutaka 岩本裕. 1985. Ta Prohm hibun ni mirareru sūchi nitsuite: Kanbojia hibun kō (1) Ta Prohm 碑文にみられる数値について:カンボジア碑文考 (1) (On the numerical values on the Ta Prohm Inscription of Jayavarman VII). *Tōnan Ajia Kenkyū* 『東南アジア研究』 (Japanese Journal of Southeast Asian Studies) 23-1:38–43.
- Jacques, Claude. 1971. Supplément au tome VIII des inscriptions du Cambodge. *Bulletin de l’École Française d’Extrême-Orient* 58-1:177–195.
- . 1999a. Les derniers siècles d’Angkor. *Comptes Rendus des Séances de l’Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres* 1999, no. 1 (janvier-mars):367–390.
- . 1999b. Les inscriptions du Phnom Kbal Spān (K 1011, 1012, 1015 et 1016): Études d’épigraphie cambodgienne, XI. *Bulletin de l’École Fran-*

- çaise d'Extrême-Orient* 86:357–374.
- . 2001. Les noms posthumes des rois dans l'ancien Cambodge. In *Fruits of inspiration: Studies in honour of Prof. J. G. de Casparis, retired professor of the early history and archeology of South and Southeast Asia at the University of Leiden, the Netherlands on the occasion of his 85th birthday*, ed. Marijke J. Klokke and Karel R. Van Kooij, 191–198. Groningen: Egbert Forsten.
- . 2002. Khmer epigraphy. *Museum International* 213–214 (v. 54, no. 1–2):37–43.
- . 2003. À propos de la découverte inespérée d'un objet inscrit au Cambodge: Une dédicace du roi Jayavarman VII en 1217. *Comptes Rendus des Séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres* 2003, no. 1 (janvier–mars):415–425.
- . 2005. Deux problèmes posés par l'inscription de la stèle de Praḥ Khan K.908. *Aséanie: Sciences humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 15:11–31.
- . 2006. The Buddhist sect of Śrīghana in ancient Khmer lands. In *Buddhist legacies in mainland Southeast Asia: Mentalities, interpretations and practices*, ed. François Lagirarde and Paritta Chalermpong Koanantakool, Études thématiques 19, SAC Publication 61, 71–77. Paris; Bangkok: École Française d'Extrême-Orient; Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn Anthropology Centre.
- . 2007a. La métrique en sanscrit. In Ishizawa et al. 2007, 23–28.
- . 2007b. The historical development of Khmer culture from the death of Suryavarman II to the 16th century. In *Bayon: New perspectives*, ed. Joyce Clark, 28–49. Bangkok: River Books.
- Jacques, Claude and Khin Sok. 2007. Inscriptions ayant principalement servi à établir l'histoire ancienne du pays khmer. In Ishizawa et al. 2007, 29–152.
- Jenner, Philip N. 1982. *A chronological inventory of the inscriptions of Cambodia, second edition, revised*. (Southeast Asia Paper No.19). Honolulu: Center for Southeast Asian Studies with the School of Hawaiian, Asian, and Pacific Studies at the University of Hawaii at Manoa. 54p.
- . 2009a. *A dictionary of pre-Angkorian Khmer*. Canberra: Pacific Linguistics, Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies, Australian National University. 620p.
- . 2009b. *A dictionary of Angkorian Khmer*. Canberra: Pacific Linguistics, Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies. Australian National University. 778p.
- Jenner, Philip N. and Paul Sidwell. 2010. *Old Khmer grammar*. Canberra: Pacific Linguistics, School of Culture, History and Language, College of Asia and the Pacific, Australian National University. 88p.
- Kanayama, Yoshio 金山好男. 1965. *Kanbodia kanken: Kanayama Yoshio ikō* 『カンボディア管見: 金山好男遺稿』 (Looking on Cambodia: Posthumous writings of Yoshio Kanayama). Tokyo (private publication).
- Kapur, Pradeep Kumar, and Sachchidanand Sahai. 2007. *Ta Prohm: A glori-*

- ous era in Angkor civilization*. Bangkok: White Lotus. 208p.
- Kern, Johan H. C. 1879. Opschriften op Oude Bouwwerken in Kambodja. *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en volkenkunde, Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences of Southeast Asia* 27-1:268–272.
- Khin Sok. 2007. Quelques principes de grammaire khmère ancienne. In Ishizawa et al. 2007, 11–22.
- Kulke, Hermann. 1993. *Kings and cults: State formation and legitimation in India and Southeast Asia*. New Delhi: Manodar.
- Lepoutre, Amandine. 2013. Études du corpus des inscriptions du Campā IV: Les inscriptions du temple de Svayamutpanna: Contribution à l’histoire des relations entre les pouvoirs cam et khmer (de la fin du XIIe siècle au début du XIIIe siècle). *Journal Asiatique* 301-1:205–278.
- Long Seam. 2000. *Dictionnaire du khmer ancien: D’après les inscriptions du Cambodge du VIe–VIIIe siècles*. Phnom Penh: Printing House.
- . 2007. Les toponymes en khmer ancien. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 19:15–74.
- Lowman, Ian. 2012. K.227 and the “Bharata Rāhu” relief: Two narratives from Banteay Chmar. In *Connecting empires and states: Selected papers from the 13th international conference of the European Association of Southeast Asian Archaeologists*, vol. 2, ed. Mai Lin Tjoa-Bonatz, Andreas Reinecke and Dominik Bonatz, 241–256. Singapore: NUS Press.
- . 2013. The elephant hunt of Jayavarman III: A political myth of Angkorian Cambodia. *Udaya: Journal of Khmer Studies* 11:29–57.
- Lustig, Eileen J. 2009. *Power and pragmatism in the political economy of Angkor*. PhD diss., University of Sydney.
- Lustig, Eileen, Damian Evans, and Ngaire Richards. 2007. Words across space and time: An analysis of lexical items in Khmer inscriptions, sixth-fourteenth centuries CE. *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies* 38-1:1–26.
- Lustig, Eileen, and Mitch Hendrickson. 2012. Angkor’s roads: An archaeological approach. In *Connecting empires and states: Selected papers from the 13th international conference of the European Association of Southeast Asian Archaeologists*, vol. 2, ed. Mai Lin Tjoa-Bonatz, Andreas Reinecke and Dominik Bonatz, 191–208. Singapore: NUS Press.
- Lustig, Eileen and Terry Lustig. 2013. New insights into ‘les interminables listes nominatives d’esclaves’ from numerical analyses of the personnel in Angkorian inscriptions. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 31:55–83.
- Majumdar, Ramesh C. 1953. *Inscriptions of Kambuja*. Calcutta: The Asiatic Society.
- Matsuura, Fumiaki 松浦史明. 2014. Ankōru no chōzō ni miru hito to kami: Kokubun shiryō no kentō kara アンコールの彫像にみる人と神: 刻文史料の検討から (Man and god as seen in sculpture of Angkor period: Based on the study of inscribed works). *Bukkyō Geijutsu 佛教藝術 (Ars Buddhica)* 337:36–55.

- Maxwell, Thomas S. 2007a. The stele inscription of Preah Khan, Angkor: Text with translation and commentary. *Udaya: Journal of Khmer Studies* 8:1–113.
- . 2007b. Religion at the time of Jayavarman VII. In *Bayon: New perspectives*, ed. Joyce Clark, 72–121. Bangkok: River Books.
- . 2007c. The short inscriptions of the Bayon and contemporary temples. In *Bayon: New perspectives*, ed. Joyce Clark, 122–135. Bangkok: River Books.
- . 2007d. *Angkor inscriptions survey and documentation, interim report 2007*. Siem Reap: Angkor Inscriptions Survey.
- . 2009. A new Khmer and Sanskrit inscription at Banteay Chmar. *Udaya: Journal of Khmer Studies* 10:135–201.
- Pichard, Pierre. 2006. L'inscription de Dharmasena à Mueang Toei (K.1082): 1. Archéologie. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 18:83–92.
- Prapandvidya, Chirapat. 1990. The Sab Bāk inscription: Evidence of an early Vajrayana buddhist presence in Thailand. *The Journal of the Siam Society* 78-2:11–14.
- Pottier, Christophe and Dominique Soutif. 2014 (actually published in 2016). De l'ancienneté de Hariharālaya: Une inscription préangkoriennne opportune à Bakong. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 100:147–166.
- Pou, Saveros. 1997. Khmer epigraphy. In *Sculpture of Angkor and ancient Cambodia: Millennium of glory*, ed. Helen I. Jessup and Thierry Zephir, 53–61. Washington: National Gallery of Art.
- . 2001. *Nouvelles inscriptions du Cambodge II & III*. Paris: École Française d'Extrême-Orient.
- . 2004. *Dictionnaire vieux khmer-français-anglais*. 2^e édition. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- . 2011. *Nouvelles inscriptions du Cambodge IV: Avec la collaboration de Grégory Mikaelian*. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- Sahai, Sachchidanand. 1970. *Les institutions politoques et l'organisation administrative du Cambodge ancien (VI^e–XIII^e siècles)*. Paris: École Française d'Extrême-Orient.
- . 2005. The Devarāja Cult: Inscriptional, art and architectural evidences from Cambodia. In *God & king: The Devarāja Cult in South Asian art & architecture*, ed. Arputha R. Sengupta, 101–118. New Delhi: National Museum Institute.
- . 2007. *The Bayon of Angkor Thom*. Bangkok: White Lotus. 146p.
- Sak-Humphry, Chhany. 2005. *The Sdok Kak Thom inscription (K.235): With a grammatical analysis of the old Khmer text*. Phnom Penh: The Buddhist Institute.
- Sanderson, Alexis. 2003–2004. The Śaiva religion among the Khmers: part I. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 90–91:349–462.
- Sharan, Mahesh K. 1974. *Studies in Sanskrit inscriptions of ancient Cambodia*. New Delhi: Abhinav Publications.

- Sharrock, Peter D. 2009. Kirtipaṇḍita and the Tantras. *Udaya: Journal of Khmer Studies* 10:203–237.
- Somporn, Thitsadee and Robert McCarthy. 2012. *Estampage of Bayon inscriptions*. Phnom Penh: Digital Advertising. 97p.
- Soutif, Dominique. 2008a. La monture de conque inscrite du Musée national de Phnom Penh: Relecture de l'inscription angkoriennne K.779. *Aséanie: Sciences Humaines en Asie du Sud-Est* 22:47–61.
- . 2008b. Dénombrer les biens du dieu: Étude de la numération du vieux khmer (VI^e–XII^e siècles śaka). *Sikṣācakr: Journal of Cambodia Research* 10:51–80.
- . 2009a. Organisation religieuse et profane du temple khmer du VIII^{ème} au XIII^{ème} siècle. PhD diss., Université Paris III, Sorbonne nouvelle.
- . 2009b. *Kanloñ* ou *Mandira*: Un palais à Purandarapura à la fin du VII^e siècle de notre ère? *Udaya: Journal of Khmer Studies* 10:239–255.
- . 2009c. À propos de trois possibles attributs mobiles dans les inscriptions khmères. *Sikṣācakr: Journal of Cambodia Research* 11:22–42.
- . 2010. Le pendentif inscrit du musée national du Cambodge: Une «bague de Rāma» datant du règne de Jayavarman VII (K.1277)? *Arts Asiatiques* 65:121–132.
- UNV/UNDP. 2002. *Ancient inscriptions of Cambodia*. 4 vols. Phnom Penh: UNESCO.
- Vickery, Michael. 1998. *Society, economics, and politics in pre-Angkor Cambodia: The 7th–8th centuries*. Tokyo: The Centre for East Asian Cultural Studies for UNESCO; The Toyo Bunko. 486p.
- . 1999. The Khmer inscriptions of Roluos (Preah Ko and Lolei): Documents from a transitional period in Cambodian history. *Seksa Khmer* (Nouvelle Série), no.1:47–92.
- . 2003. Funan reviewed: Deconstructing the ancients. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 90-1:101–143.
- . 2007. L'inscription thaï du Phnom Kulên, K 1006. In Ishizawa et al. 2007, 155–167.
- Vong Sotheara. 2010. *Pre-Angkorian inscriptions of Cambodia 1*. 2nd ed. Phnom Penh: Editions Angkor.
- . 2011. *Inscriptions du Cambodge: Anthologie épigraphies anciennes du Cambodge (transliteration internationale)*. 2 vols. Phnom Penh: Editions Angkor.
- . 2017. Hierarchy in ancient Cambodia: The study of title nouns. PhD diss., Sophia University.
- Weber, Nicolas. 2014 (actually published in 2016). Note sur les inscriptions en cam du *paḷāt'* Tut: Estampeur d'Étienne Aymonier. *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient* 100:253–258.
- Woodward, Hiram W. Jr. 2001. Practice and belief in ancient Cambodia: Claude Jacques' *Angkor* and the *Devarāja* question. *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies* 32-2:249–261.